

Normal İşitmeye Sahip Tinnituslu Adölesan Hastalarda İmmitansmetrik Ölçüm ve Akustik Refleks Testlerinin Değerlendirmesi

Evaluation of Immittance Measurement and Acoustic Reflex Tests in Normal Hearing Adolescent Patients with Tinnitus

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Özet

Akustik direnç, orta kulağa timpanik membran ve kemikçikler vasıtasıyla gelen ses enerjisini bir kısmına direnç gösterip geri yansıtması olayıdır. Bu çalışmanın amacı, normal işitmeye sahip adölesanlarda immittansmetrik ölçüm ve akustik refleks test sonuçlarının normal değerlerini ortaya koymak ve tinnitus şikayeti olan hastalar ile elde edilen sonuçlarla karşılaştırmaktır. Bu çalışmaya 10-19 yaş arası toplam 61 kız, 58 erkek olmak üzere toplam 119 gönüllü katılmıştır. Otoskopik muayeneleri normal bulgulara sahip olanlar çalışmaya dahil edilmiştir. Çalışmaya katılan 21 adölesanın tek kulaklarında tinnitus şikayeti mevcuttur. Tüm ölçümler Maico MI-34 H timpanometre cihazı ile yapılmıştır. İmmittansmetrik ölçümlerde kanal volümü, komplians, orta kulak basıncı ve gradient değerlendirilmiştir. Akustik refleks ölçümleri ise ipsi ve kontralateral olarak 500- 4000 Hz arasında her iki kulak için ayrı ayrı yapılmıştır. Tinnitus, dolgunluk ve gürültü ortamlarda anlama problemlerinde akustik refleks eşiklerinin yükselmesi bu durumun bir göstergesi olabilir. Çalışmaya katılan ve herhangi bir sağlık problemi olmayan adölesanların sağ ve sol kulakları için ipsilateral akustik refleks eşikleri 90-95 dB arasında, kontralateral akustik refleks eşikleri ise 95-100 dB arasında elde edilmiştir. Tinnitus şikayeti olan ve olmayan adölesanların 500- 4000 Hz arası ipsilateral akustik refleks eşik karşılaştırmasında sol kulak 500, 1000, 2000 ve 4000 Hz'de istatistiksel olarak anlamlı bir fark mevcut iken kontralateral akustik refleks eşik karşılaştırmasında sağ kulak 500, 2000 ve 4000 Hz'de ve sol kulak 2000 Hz' de istatistiksel olarak anlamlı bir fark mevcuttur ($p<0.05$). İmmittansmetrik ölçümlerde ise kanal volümleri ortalama 0.96 ml, kompliansları ortalama 0.73 ml, orta kulak basınçları ortalama -47 daPa ve gradient değerleri ortalama 78 daPa olarak elde edilmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Normal işitme; tinnitus; adölesan; akustik refleks; immittansmetrik ölçüm.

Abstract

Acoustic resistance is the phenomenon where part of the sound energy transmitted to the middle ear via the tympanic membrane and ossicles is resisted and reflected back. This study aims to establish normal immittance and acoustic reflex values in adolescents with normal hearing and compare them with those of adolescents experiencing tinnitus. A total of 119 adolescents aged 10 to 19 (61 females, 58 males) participated in the study. Only individuals with normal otoscopic findings were included. Among them, 21 reported unilateral tinnitus complaints. All measurements were conducted using a Maico MI-34 H tympanometer. Immittance evaluations included ear canal volume, compliance, middle ear pressure, and gradient. Acoustic reflex thresholds were measured ipsilaterally and contralaterally for both ears at frequencies ranging from 500 to 4000 Hz. In adolescents without hearing complaints, ipsilateral acoustic reflex thresholds ranged between 90–95 dB, and contralateral thresholds between 95–100 dB. Elevated acoustic reflex thresholds may reflect auditory issues such as tinnitus, aural fullness, or difficulty understanding speech in noisy environments. Statistically significant differences were observed when comparing adolescents with and without tinnitus. For ipsilateral reflex thresholds, significant differences were found in the left ear at 500, 1000, 2000, and 4000 Hz. Contralateral thresholds showed significant differences at 500, 2000, and 4000 Hz in the right ear, and at 2000 Hz in the left ear ($p<0.05$). Mean immittance values were: ear canal volume 0.96 ml, compliance 0.73 ml, middle ear pressure -47 daPa, and gradient 78 daPa.

Keywords: Normal hearing; tinnitus; adolescent; acoustic reflex; immittance measurement.

1. Introduction

According to the definition accepted by ANSI (American National Standards Institute), tympanometry is the process of measuring acoustic immittance in the external ear canal as a function of air pressure in the external ear canal (Özgirgin & Çelik, 2002). Tympanometry evaluates compliance, which refers to the vibration amplitude of the tympanic membrane in response to pressure changes in the external ear canal.

The tympanometry test is performed by connecting a probe to the external ear canal and varying the pressure using a manometer between +200 daPa and -400 daPa. The graph that displays compliance values according to pressure changes in the external ear canal as a result of tympanometry is called a tympanogram (Rosowski & Wilber, 2015).

The horizontal axis of the tympanogram represents the pressure applied to the external auditory canal, while the vertical axis shows the compliance values.

When the initial pressure applied is +200 mm, the tympanic membrane and ossicles are pushed forward, resulting in a loss of mobility. As a result, almost all of the applied sound is reflected back from the membrane due to reduced mobility. In this condition, compliance is at its minimum value, and impedance is at its maximum.

As the pressure applied to the external auditory canal (EAC) is decreased, the mobile structures of the middle ear begin to relax, and an increase in compliance is observed up to a certain point. The compliance value peaks and then decreases again.

The resulting peak indicates that the pressure applied to the EAC is equal to the pressure in the middle ear. If the Eustachian tube is functioning normally, this peak will occur at approximately 0 mm (Rosowski & Wilber, 2015).

The analysis of the tympanogram includes classification based on the presence or absence of a peak, the pressure value at the peak, and the amplitude of the peak. The first study on tympanogram classification was conducted by Liden (1969) and later developed by Jerger et al. (1972) and Liden et al. (1974). Among these, the most widely accepted classification is the modification proposed by Jerger (1970), which remains the most commonly used. This classification is applicable for low-frequency tympanometry, particularly at 226 Hz (Shahnaz et al., 2023).

Tinnitus is the perception of sound in the absence of a corresponding external acoustic stimulus, perceived either continuously or intermittently (Eggermont & Roberts, 2004; Langguth, Kreuzer, Kleinjung, & De Ridder, 2013). It is one of the most common symptoms in otolaryngology and is difficult to evaluate objectively, with its etiology not yet fully understood.

Due to its distressing nature, tinnitus can lead to various health-related problems such as sleep disturbances, lack of concentration, and potentially depression and anxiety. These serious complications can negatively affect quality of life and, in extreme cases, may lead to suicidal thoughts or actions (Mahafza, Zhao, El Refaie, & Chen, 2021). Studies have shown that individuals with tinnitus and normal hearing thresholds often report

difficulty understanding speech, especially in noisy environments, and perform worse on speech-in-noise tests compared to individuals without tinnitus (Huang et al., 2007).

The aim of this study is to evaluate immittance measurements and acoustic reflex tests in adolescents with tinnitus who have normal hearing, and to contribute to and support future research in this field.

2. Method

2.1. Ethical approval:

This study was conducted at the Audiology and Speech Disorders Unit of Turgut Özal University. Ethics committee approval dated 10/02/2016 and numbered 99950669/42 was granted by Turgut Özal University Faculty of Medicine Clinical Research Ethics Committee. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants, and the tests were explained in detail. Audiological tests were administered to the adolescents who agreed to participate in the study.

A total of 119 individuals (mean age: 14.403 ± 3.13), aged between 10 and 19 years, participated in the study. Following the Ear, Nose, and Throat (ENT) examination, participants underwent pure-tone audiometry (Interacoustics AC 40 Audiometer, Assens, Denmark), immittance measurements, and acoustic reflex testing (MAICO MI 34-H Tympanometer, Assens, Germany).

Participants were included in the study if their routine ENT examination was normal, they had no otological problems, and their hearing thresholds were <15 dB HL based on the pure-tone average. Additionally, both air and bone conduction hearing thresholds needed to be within normal limits.

2.2. During immittance measurements

The external ear canal was sealed using a probe selected in accordance with the canal size, and the measurement was conducted automatically. Using a probe tone of 226 Hz at 85 dB SPL, and applying pressure between +200 daPa and -400 daPa, the following parameters were evaluated:

- Ear canal volume
- Compliance
- Middle ear pressure
- Gradient values

2.3. Acoustic reflex measurements

Based on the immittance results, ipsilateral and contralateral acoustic reflexes were examined in individuals with normal (Type A) tympanogram findings, within the frequency range of 500–4000 Hz. Middle ear pressure was considered normal between +50 daPa and -100 daPa. The device performed assessments based on the middle ear pressure obtained from the immittance measurements.

Ipsilateral measurements were taken first, followed by contralateral measurements, and the acoustic reflex threshold levels were determined. Additionally, a reflex decay test was performed contralaterally at 500 Hz.

In this test, a stimulus 10 dB above the acoustic reflex threshold was delivered through headphones for 10 seconds. Reflex decay was classified as **positive** or **negative** based on the response.

2.4. Statistical analysis:

Statistical calculations were performed using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) for Windows, version 20.0. Descriptive statistics, including means and standard deviations, were calculated. In addition to the **t-test**, the **Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test** was used to determine whether the distributions of two different groups came from the same population. The resulting *p*-value was compared with the significance level (α), which was set at 0.05 for this analysis.

3. Result

The demographic characteristics of participants are Male participants N:58 Female participants N:61. There were no significant gender differences were detected regarding age variation ($p > 0.05$).

Ipsilateral acoustic reflex thresholds between 500-4000 Hz of adolescents having tinnitus complaints (21 people) and without tinnitus complaints (98 people) are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Ipsilateral acoustic reflex measurements of adolescents with and without tinnitus complaints

Ipsilateral	Control group		Experimental group		p value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Right 500 Hz	92.60	7.50	95.95	7.84	0.377
Left 500 Hz	91.68	8.15	96.19	4.44	0.014
Right 1000 Hz	93.72	7.29	95.47	9.34	0.556
Left 1000 Hz	94.18	6.40	98.81	2.69	0.000
Right 2000 Hz	93.52	7.39	93.81	9.34	0.400
Left 2000 Hz	93.62	7.62	99.04	3.39	0.000
Right 4000 Hz	93.72	4.20	92.61	6.04	0.079
Left 4000 Hz	92.75	6.13	95.00	0.00	0.000

There is a statistically significant difference in the left ear 500, 1000, 2000 and 4000 Hz ($p < 0.05$) according to the values given in Table 1.

In the comparison of the ipsilateral acoustic reflex threshold between 500 and 4000 Hz of adolescents with tinnitus complaints (21 people) and without tinnitus complaints (98 people).

Contralateral acoustic reflex thresholds between 500-4000 Hz of adolescents with tinnitus complaints (21 people) and without tinnitus complaints (98 people) are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Contralateral acoustic reflex measurements of adolescents with and without tinnitus complaints.

Contrateral	Control group		Experimental group		p value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Right 500 Hz	97.24	10.48	104.04	6.04	0.002
Left 500 Hz	96.58	11.54	97.85	11.68	0.625
Right 1000 Hz	97.65	9.92	101.19	8.78	0.274
Left 1000 Hz	96.48	10.94	99.52	9.86	0.217
Right 2000 Hz	98.52	10.43	102.14	7.17	0.049
Left 2000 Hz	98.16	10.33	97.85	13.37	0.044
Right 4000 Hz	101.99	10.64	106.42	5.50	0.002
Left 4000 Hz	101.83	10.11	101.66	12.48	0.653

In the contralateral acoustic reflex threshold comparison between 500-4000 Hz, there is a statistically significant difference in the right ear at 500, 2000 and 4000 Hz and the left ear at 2000 Hz ($p < 0.05$) according to the values given in Table 2.

Right and left ear canal volume, compliance, pressure and gradient immittance measurement values of adolescents with (21 people) and without (98 people) complaints of tinnitus are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Immittansmetric measurements of adolescents with and without tinnitus complaints.

Immittansmetry	Control grup		Experimental group		p value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Right ear volume (ml)	0.98	0.51	1.00	0.60	0.687
Left ear volume (ml)	0.95	0.41	0.89	0.38	0.516
Right compliance (ml)	0.65	0.39	0.56	0.41	0.582
Left compliance (ml)	0.63	0.32	0.48	0.29	0.447
Right pressure (daPa)	-45.55	63.36	-43.71	51.68	0.473
Left pressure (daPa)	-51.27	67.59	-53.66	83.09	0.526
Right gradient (daPa)	84.39	54.31	106.47	72.63	0.132
Left gradient (daPa)	88.65	49.90	112.14	73.40	0.130

According to the values given in Table 3; No statistically significant difference is observed in the immittansmetric values of adolescents with tinnitus complaints (21 people) and without tinnitus complaints (98 people) ($p < 0.05$).

The ipsilateral acoustic reflex thresholds between 500 and 4000 Hz of adolescents with tinnitus complaints (8 males) and without tinnitus complaints (50 males) are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Ipsilateral acoustic reflex measurements of male adolescents with and without tinnitus complaints.

Ipsilateral	Control grup		Experimental group		p value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Right 500 Hz	91.70	7.86	97.59	4.62	0.101
Left 500 Hz	91.70	7.79	97.50	3.77	0.030
Right 1000 Hz	93.90	6.79	100.00	0.00	0.000
Left 1000 Hz	94.40	5.49	100.00	0.00	0.000
Right 2000 Hz	93.60	7.14	96.87	3.72	0.049
Left 2000 Hz	94.00	6.62	99.37	1.76	0.002
Right 4000 Hz	93.30	4.90	93.75	3.53	0.611
Left 4000 Hz	93.50	5.36	95.00	0.00	0.107

According to the values given in Table 4; In the ipsilateral acoustic reflex threshold comparison between 500 and 4000 Hz of adolescents with tinnitus complaints (8 males) and without tinnitus complaints (50 males), a statistically significant difference is observed in the right ear at 1000 and 2000 Hz and the left ear at 500, 1000 and 2000 Hz ($p < 0.05$).

Contralateral acoustic reflex thresholds between 500 and 4000 Hz of adolescents with tinnitus complaints (8 males) and without tinnitus complaints (50 males) are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Contralateral acoustic reflex measurements of male adolescents with and without tinnitus complaints.

Contrateral	Control grup		Experimental group		p value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Right 500 Hz	96.50	9.85	104.37	5.63	0.029
Left 500 Hz	94.90	11.53	100.00	6.54	0.047
Right 1000 Hz	95.00	9.36	100.62	4.95	0.060
Left 1000 Hz	94.00	11.01	99.37	7.28	0.114
Right 2000 Hz	97.20	10.45	102.50	7.07	0.099
Left 2000 Hz	96.70	8.89	100.62	10.50	0.352
Right 4000 Hz	102.00	10.49	108.12	2.58	0.006
Left 4000 Hz	101.90	9.52	105.00	5.34	0.049

According to the values given in Table 5; In the contralateral acoustic reflex threshold comparison between 500-4000 Hz of adolescents with tinnitus complaints (8 males) and without tinnitus complaints (50 males), a statistically significant difference is observed in the right and left ear at 500 Hz and the right and left ear at 4000 Hz ($p < 0.05$).

Right and left ear canal volume, compliance, pressure and gradient immittance measurement values of adolescents with tinnitus complaints (8 males) and without tinnitus complaints (50 males) are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. *Immittansmetric measurements of male adolescents with and without tinnitus complaints.*

Immittansmetri	Control group		Experimental group		p value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Right ear volume (ml)	1.09	0.53	1.43	0.75	0.134
Left ear volume (ml)	1.02	0.34	0.92	0.29	0.401
Right compliance (ml)	0.64	0.30	0.72	0.58	0.000
Left compliance (ml)	0.63	0.26	0.41	0.23	0.636
Right pressure (daPa)	-32.98	48.38	-24.62	20.83	0.329
Left pressure (daPa)	-43.76	66.56	-35.25	29.41	0.294
Right gradient (daPa)	90.94	67.48	119.37	64.31	0.428
Left gradient (daPa)	92.40	57.74	127.37	56.07	0.640

According to the values given in Table 6; The right compliance (ml) values in the immittansmetric values of adolescents with tinnitus complaints (8 males) and without tinnitus complaints (50 males) are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The ipsilateral acoustic reflex thresholds between 500 and 4000 Hz of adolescents with tinnitus complaints (13 female) and without tinnitus complaints (48 female) are shown in Table 7.

Table 7. *Ipsilateral acoustic reflex measurements of female adolescents with and without tinnitus complaints.*

Ipsilateral	Control group		Experimental group		p value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Right 500 Hz	93.54	7.06	95.00	9.35	0.965
Left 500 Hz	91.66	8.58	95.38	4.77	0.100
Right 1000 Hz	93.54	7.85	92.69	11.10	0.133
Left 1000 Hz	93.95	7.29	98.07	3.25	0.037
Right 2000 Hz	93.43	7.72	91.92	11.28	0.049
Left 2000 Hz	93.22	8.59	98.84	4.16	0.003
Right 4000 Hz	94.16	3.31	91.92	7.22	0.005
Left 4000 Hz	91.97	6.82	95.00	0.00	0.002

According to the values given in Table 7; In the ipsilateral acoustic reflex threshold comparison between 500 and 4000 Hz of adolescents with tinnitus complaints (13 female) and without tinnitus complaints (48 female), a statistically significant difference is observed in the right ear 2000 and 4000 Hz and the left ear 1000, 2000 and 4000 Hz ($p < 0.05$).

Contralateral acoustic reflex thresholds between 500 and 4000 Hz of adolescents with tinnitus complaints (13 female) and without tinnitus complaints (48 female) are shown in Table 8.

Table 8. *Contralateral acoustic reflex measurements of female adolescents with and without tinnitus complaints.*

Contralateral	Control group		Experimental group		p value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Right 500 Hz	98.02	11.14	103.84	6.50	0.033
Left 500 Hz	98.33	11.40	96.53	14.05	0.391
Right 1000 Hz	100.41	9.83	101.53	10.68	0.589
Left 1000 Hz	99.06	10.34	99.61	11.44	0.728
Right 2000 Hz	99.89	10.33	101.92	7.51	0.374
Left 2000 Hz	99.68	11.55	96.15	15.02	0.121
Right 4000 Hz	101.97	10.90	105.38	6.60	0.080
Left 4000 Hz	101.77	10.79	99.61	15.20	0.162

According to the values given in Table 8; In the comparison of the contralateral acoustic reflex threshold between 500-4000 Hz of adolescents with tinnitus complaints (13 females) and without tinnitus complaints (48 females), a statistically significant difference is observed in the right ear at 500 Hz ($p < 0.05$).

Right and left ear canal volume, compliance, pressure, and gradient immittance measurement values of adolescents with tinnitus complaints (13 female) and without tinnitus complaints (48 female) are shown in Table 9.

Table 9. *Immittansmetric measurements of female adolescents with and without tinnitus complaints.*

Immittansmetri	Control group		Experimental group		p value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Right ear volume (ml)	0.88	0.46	0.73	0.26	0.161
Left ear volume (ml)	0.87	0.45	0.88	0.44	0.747
Right compliance (ml)	0.65	0.46	0.47	0.24	0.182
Left compliance (ml)	0.63	0.39	0.53	0.32	0.412
Right pressure (daPa)	-58.64	74.17	-55.46	61.69	0.678
Left pressure (daPa)	-59.10	68.47	-65.00	103.06	0.111
Right gradient (daPa)	77.58	35.33	98.53	78.75	0.166
Left gradient (daPa)	84.75	40.41	102.76	83.04	0.118

According to the values given in Table 9; No statistical significance was observed in the immittansmetric values of adolescents with tinnitus complaints (13 female) and without tinnitus complaints (48 female) ($p < 0.05$).

4. Discussion

Production and measurement standards of acoustic immittance meters are carried out in accordance with ANSI S3.39-1987. Immittance measurements not only show the mechanical effects of the outer and middle

ear, but also show the muscle responses, auditory and facial nerve activities in the middle ear (Katz, 2015). The middle ear system is a system that converts acoustic energy into mechanical energy. In addition to mechanical system evaluation, it enables observation of the current impact on the system (Hamra, et al. 2024). The Ear, Nose and Throat medical examination is absolutely necessary before acoustic immittance measurement. Immitansmetric examination alone has no diagnostic value. A low external ear canal volume indicates that this area is filled with a plug(cerumen) or similar material or that the probe is leaning against a wall in the external ear canal. A very large external ear canal volume also indicates tympanic membrane perforation. Because, due to a perforation in the tympanic membrane, the middle ear and outer ear canal have become a whole. Therefore, the volume will be higher than it is. Acoustic immittance is a general name given to the components of acoustic impedance and acoustic admittance. The term acoustics determines the characteristics of the energy system being measured (Musiek, 1999).

Tığ O. (2022) evaluated the results of wide-band tympanometry in tinnitus patients with normal hearing in his master's thesis. An adult group (18-65 years old) was included in this study, and the results of the study conducted on 80 individuals with wide-band tympanometry were compatible with our study data. In Tığ's study, it was found that the ambient pressure absorbance value at 4000 Hz frequency in the left ear was significantly higher in patients with tinnitus whose ear side variable was right, compared to patients with tinnitus whose ear side was left and bilateral.

Acoustic immittance measurements are made with a tympanometer device. Acoustic immittance measurements are the dynamic measurement of acoustic immittance with functional changes of air pressure in the external auditory canal. The most important reason for tympanometry is to determine the presence and potential cause of middle ear diseases. Tympanometry has been routinely performed in clinics since the 1970s (Shahnaz et al., 2023). There are two important criteria in tympanogram evaluation: The amplitude (compliance) of the tympanometric peak and the pressure value of the peak (middle ear pressure) (Katz, 2015).

For the acoustic reflex to occur; the air conduction, cochlea, auditory nerve, superior oliveri complex and brainstem of the ear to given stimulus, the facial nerve, stapedius nerve, stapes muscle and middle ear of the ear from which the reflex will be received must be normal. When the acoustic reflex occurs, the front part of the base of the stapes ossicle turns laterally and the back part turns medially. Thus, by fixing the stapes base, the sound intensity passing into the middle ear is reduced (Rawool, 2025).

In addition, the gradient value in immitansmetric measurements also provides information about middle ear functions. In some cases, even if the middle ear pressure is within normal limits, a low gradient value suggests an effusion or fluid accumulation in the middle ear.

According to the data in our study, when comparing the right and left ear ipsilateral acoustic reflex thresholds of adolescents with and without any ear complaints, there is a statistically significant difference in the left 1000 Hz and 4000 Hz and the right 4000 Hz ($p<0.05$). High acoustic reflex thresholds were attributed to an effect on the ipsilateral acoustic reflex arc.

In the comparison of the contralateral acoustic reflex threshold between 500-4000 Hz of adolescents with and without any ear complaints, there is a statistically significant difference between the right ear contralateral 4000 Hz and the left ear contralateral 4000 Hz ($p < 0.05$). It is thought that this situation is caused by the 7th nerve being affected in the ipsi and contralateral acoustic reflex arc.

There is a statistically significant difference in the right and left compliance (ml) and right and left gradient (daPa) values of adolescents with and without any ear complaints ($p < 0.05$). Low right and left compliance values indicate that the movement of the middle ear system is limited. The reason for this is (SOM) Serous otitis media experienced in childhood, antibiotics (drugs) used, etc. linked to problems. Low right and left ear gradient values indicate a tendency for middle ear infection.

In the comparison of the ipsilateral acoustic reflex threshold between 500 and 4000 Hz of adolescents with tinnitus complaints (21 people) and without tinnitus complaints (98 people), there is a statistically significant difference in the left ear at 500, 1000, 2000 and 4000 Hz ($p < 0.05$). It shows that there is a partial effect on the ipsilateral acoustic reflex arc.

In the contralateral acoustic reflex threshold comparison between 500-4000 Hz of adolescents with tinnitus complaints (21 people) and without tinnitus complaints (98 people), there is a statistically significant difference in the right ear at 500, 2000 and 4000 Hz and the left ear at 2000 Hz ($p < 0.05$).

No statistically significant difference is observed in the immittance values of adolescents with tinnitus complaints (21 people) and without tinnitus complaints (98 people) ($p < 0.05$). The fact that; there is no significant difference between individuals with and without tinnitus in immittance measurements has shown that the source of tinnitus may be the acoustic reflex arc in ipsi and contralateral reflexes.

The right compliance (ml) values in the immittance values of adolescents with tinnitus complaints (8 males) and without tinnitus complaints (50 males) are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

The difference in only the right compliance value suggests that the middle ear functions are normal and the tinnitus complaint may be of more central origin.

As a result of the immittance examination, it was observed that female individuals were less affected than male individuals. This may be related to the fact that the number of male individuals complaining of tinnitus is lower than female individuals.

Every measurement of auditory function depends on the frequency of the stimulus. The most important reason why hearing sensitivity depends on frequency is that the sound transfer to the middle ear is related to frequency. Immittance, which is related to mass and stiffness, is significantly frequency dependent (Musiek, Rintelman, 1999).

5. Conclusions

As a result, immittance measurement is one of the key tests in audiological examinations. It supports the reliability of the information it provides about the outer and middle ear, as well as the results of other tests such as otoacoustic emissions, brainstem responses, and auditory brainstem response (ABR). For this reason,

immittance testing should be conducted under precise and controlled conditions. We believe that the findings of this study contribute to the existing body of knowledge and may serve as a valuable reference for future research focusing on the adolescent population, a group in which subclinical auditory pathologies may often go undetected with conventional hearing tests alone. Further investigations with larger sample sizes and expanded test batteries are recommended to build upon the insights gained from this research.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this study.

Funding

The authors received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this study.

Authors' Contributions

Conceptualization, formal analysis, investigation, project administration, writing – original draft: Şuayb Küçük;

Formal analysis, investigation, writing – review & editing: Tuğçe Gül Çağlar

Acknowledgements

The authors declare that there are no acknowledgements to disclose.

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